

Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometric techniques in the elemental and isotopic analysis of lanthanides and actinides

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Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) and the subsequently developed high resolution inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (HR-ICP-MS) are the new instrumental analytical techniques that have made a mark during the last 15 years in the area of precise estimation of elemental and isotopic concentrations of not only lanthanides and actinides but also several other elements even when these elements are present at very low levels in different materials. A brief account of the usefulness of ICP-MS and HR-ICP-MS in the analysis of lanthanides and actinides in different materials is provided. The advantages of laser ablation (LA) sample introduction system and the use of high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) in conjunction with these two plasma mass spectrometric techniques are discussed. The advantages of the plasma source mass spectrometric techniques over the techniques, such as instrumental neutron activation analysis (INAA) and thermal ionization mass spectrometry (TIMS) for the precise estimation of lanthanides and actinides in geological, environmental and nuclear materials are presented.

Recent developments in basic materials research, and analysis of geological, nuclear, and industrial materials have placed new demands on the field of metal analysis. For instance, trace concentrations of undesirable metal atoms can effect the production and quality of high purity substances, such as nuclear fuels, high power laser, semiconductor and superconducting materials, the fabrication of which requires accurate estimation of trace metal concentrations even at sub-parts per trillion range. It is known that the chemical behavior of lanthanides or rare earth elements (REE) is governed by the systematic contraction of trivalent ionic radii with atomic number as the shielded electrons are added to the inner *4f* shell, and cerium and europium can occur in oxidation states other than +III, the main oxidation state of the group. This anomalous behavior of cerium and europium together with the coherent behavior of the rest of the series is used extensively as a tool to understand geochemical processes within Earth's mantle and crust as well as natural waters. It is very important to measure long-lived radio nuclides in our environment very accurately and precisely. Plutonium is one such element which is highly toxic and has been released into the environment by nuclear weapon testing, by satellite and reactor accidents, and from nuclear facilities. The isotopic composition of Pu in environmental samples is characteristic of its origin. Americium and curium are strategic elements in nuclear fuel cycle. They form a major source of radiation and of long living radio toxic waste. Measurement of their abundance is a primary necessity in the management of nuclear waste and for environmental pollu-

tion monitoring¹. For these studies the isotopic composition and the amount of Pu, Am and Cm must also be known with high accuracy and precision. Such information on the behavior of these nuclides in the environment is indispensable in identifying the source and for estimating the hazardous effects of radiation on humans. Conventional radiometric methods however are time-consuming and tedious owing to the low concentrations and low specific activity of these nuclides. A range of mass spectrometric techniques are available at present to meet such demands. Thermal ionization mass spectrometry (TIMS), spark source mass spectrometry (SSMS), glow discharge mass spectrometry (GDMS), laser ionization mass spectrometry (LIMS), secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS), accelerator mass spectrometry (AMS), inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) and sector field or high resolution inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (HR-ICP-MS) are some of the important mass spectrometric techniques employed in the analysis of lanthanides and actinides. Among these, ICP-MS and the recently developed HR-ICP-MS have made a mark during the last 15 years in the precise estimation of elemental and isotopic abundances of not only lanthanides and actinides but also several other elements across the periodic table even when these elements are present at very low concentration levels in different materials².

Analysis of REE, Th, U, Am and Cm by conventional ICP-MS

Developed due to the pioneering work of Houk and

Table 1. Rare earth elements, uranium and thorium concentrations ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in rock reference sample obtained using ICP-MS in comparison with certified data^a

Element	G-2 (Granite)		W-2 (Diabase)		JB-2 (Basalt)		MRG-1 (Gabbro)	
	ICP-MS value ^b	Certified value ^c						
La	88.44	89.0	11.12	11.40	2.49	2.37	9.71	9.80
Ce	157.76	160.0	23.50	24.00	6.66	6.77	25.95	26.00
Pr	16.38	18.0	5.90	5.9	1.04	0.94	3.52	3.40
Nd	55.45	55.0	13.26	14.00	6.81	6.7	19.48	19.20
Sm	7.38	7.2	3.40	3.25	2.19	2.25	4.66	4.5
Eu	1.50	1.4	1.15	1.1	0.90	0.86	1.41	1.39
Gd	4.20	4.30	3.69	3.6	3.22	3.28	4.01	4.0
Tb	0.51	0.48	0.64	0.63	0.59	0.62	0.54	0.51
Dy	2.62	2.41	3.68	3.80	3.89	3.66	2.86	2.90
Ho	0.38	0.4	0.76	0.76	0.83	0.81	0.54	0.49
Er	0.97	0.92	2.35	2.5	2.68	2.63	1.18	1.12
Tm	0.16	0.18	0.35	0.38	0.45	0.45	0.13	0.11
Yb	0.75	0.80	2.10	2.05	2.78	2.51	0.63	0.60
Lu	0.11	0.11	0.31	0.33	0.40	0.39	0.12	0.12
Th	26.13	24.7	2.29	2.2	0.33	0.33	0.87	0.93
U	2.04	2.07	0.52	0.53	0.20	0.16	0.28	0.24

SY-2 (Syenite) was used for calibration, ¹⁰³Rh and ²⁰⁹Bi were used as internal standards; G-2, W-2 from US Geological Survey; JB-2 from Geological Survey of Japan; SY-2, MRG-1 from Canadian Certified Reference Materials Project; average precision <5% RSD; samples were dissolved using microwave dissolution method.

^aRef. 8. ^bAverage of six values. ^cRef. 41.

Table 2. The isotopes of REE, Th, Np, U and Pu and used for analysis and potential oxide, hydroxide, doubly charged and other ion interfering species^a and the resolution settings required to resolves these spectral interferences by HR-ICP-MS

Isotope	Abundance %	Oxide, hydroxide and other polyatomic interfering species	Required resolution to separate spectral interferences HR-ICP-MS
¹³⁹ La	99.911	¹²³ TeO, ¹²³ SbO	10000
¹⁴⁰ Ce	88.480	¹²⁴ TeO, ¹²⁴ SnO	57000
¹⁴¹ Pr	100.00	¹²⁵ TeO	16976
¹⁴⁶ Nd	17.190	¹³⁰ BaO, ⁹⁸ RuO ₃	12177
¹⁴⁷ Sm	15.070	¹³⁰ BaOH, ⁹⁹ RuO ₃	22954
¹⁵¹ Eu	47.770	¹³⁵ BaO	7828
¹⁵⁷ Gd	15.680	¹⁴¹ PrO, ¹³⁸ BF	7334
¹⁵⁹ Tb	100.00	¹⁴³ NdO	7709
¹⁶³ Dy	24.970	¹⁴⁷ SmO	8613
¹⁶⁵ Ho	100.000	¹⁴⁹ SmO	9049
¹⁶⁶ Er	33.410	¹⁵⁰ SmO, ¹⁵⁰ NdO	9656
¹⁶⁹ Tm	100.000	¹⁵³ EuO	9349
¹⁷⁴ Yb	31.800	¹⁵⁸ DyO, ¹⁵⁸ GdO	13500
¹⁷⁵ Lu	97.400	¹⁵⁹ TbO	8524
²³² Th	100.00	-	-
²³⁷ Np	-	-	400
²³⁸ U	99.275	-	-
²³⁹ Pu	-	²³⁸ UH	400

^aRef. 19.

Gray and others³⁻⁵, ICP-MS has now become a method of popular choice for routine elemental and isotopic analysis of lanthanides and actinides in a wide range of materials over a broad range of concentrations^{6,7}. Table 1 provides the REE, U and Th concentrations obtained by using ICP-MS

in a few international rock reference samples. The samples were dissolved using microwave digestion method⁸. High sensitivity coupled with relatively simple spectra and capability to analyze all the 14 REE has made ICP-MS more attractive than other techniques, such as inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES), X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (XRF), TIMS or instrumental neutron activation analysis (INAA)⁹⁻¹². The feasibility of the analysis of REE, Th and U in rocks by ICP-MS was first demonstrated by Date and Gray¹³, using acid-digested sample solutions. Later several workers published a variety of schemes¹⁴⁻¹⁶ for the precise estimation of these elements in a variety of geological samples. Table 2 shows the various isotopes normally used for the analysis and potential oxide and hydroxide and doubly charged ion interference species. Normally, the oxide formation levels will be monitored by barium, as this forms the worst case of oxide ion interference, and measurement conditions have to be optimized for a minimum oxide, ion ratio ($\text{BaO}^+ \cdot \text{Ba}^+ < 0\%$) to minimize interference effects¹⁷. Mathematical correction can be applied wherever these effects are significant. Dulski¹⁸ gave a good description of the interference effects of oxide, hydroxide and chloride species, and correction procedures in the determination of REE in geological samples. Apart from these corrections, internal standardization, isotope-dilution, standard-addition method, and application of matrix matching reference materials for calibration, etc., are employed to get highly precise REE data in geological samples¹⁹. Tables 3 and 4 present REE data obtained using ICP-MS in a basalt reference sample, and a couple of basaltic rocks from Globoke

Balaram : Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometric techniques in the elemental and isotopic analysis *etc.*

Table 3. REE data ($\mu\text{g/g}$) obtained by ICP-MS on the basalt rock standard, BCR-1 (Columbia River Basalt, USGS) in comparison with data obtained by other analytical techniques

Element	ICP-MS values ^a	ICP-AES values ^b	INAA values ^c	IDMS values ^d	Recommended values ^e
La	25.59 ± 0.18	26.6 ± 0.2	25.80 ± 1.37	25.5 ± 0.9	25
Ce	53.59 ± 0.61	53.8 ± 0.2	51.74 ± 1.97	54.0 ± 0.8	53.7
Pr	7.00 ± 0.08	7.29 ± 0.06	NA	NA	6.9
Nd	29.03 ± 0.26	29.7 ± 0.3	29.08 ± 0.63	28.6 ± 0.5	28.7
Sm	6.79 ± 0.16	6.7 ± 0.3	6.64 ± 0.14	6.7 ± 0.2	6.6
Eu	2.07 ± 0.06	1.98 ± 0.08	1.95 ± 0.07	1.95 ± 0.03	1.96
Gd	7.67 ± 0.19	6.90 ± 0.2	7.00 ± 0.80	6.63 ± 0.08	6.7
Tb	1.07 ± 0.05	1.00 ± 0.1	1.05 ± 0.05	NA	1.05
Dy	6.39 ± 0.19	6.72 ± 0.08	NA	6.3 ± 0.1	6.35
Ho	1.41 ± 0.03	1.4 ± 0.02	NA	NA	1.25
Er	3.62 ± 0.10	3.80 ± 0.03	NA	3.61 ± 0.09	3.6
Tm	0.57 ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.02	NA	NA	0.59
Yb	3.39 ± 0.04	3.70 ± 0.03	3.18 ± 0.05	3.39 ± 0.04	3.39
Lu	0.48 ± 0.02	0.524 ± 0.004	0.57 ± 0.06	0.54 ± 0.03	0.51

NA = not available. ^aRef. 42. ^bRef. 43. ^cRef. 11. ^dRef. 12. ^eRef. 41.

Lake, Siberian Platform, Russia. Our laboratory undertook an International Proficiency Test²⁰ during 1996 and analyzed a microgranite reference sample (G94) using ICP-MS for its trace element contents along with about 60 other laboratories from 21 countries. Results obtained when the microgranite sample was analyzed for REE, Th and U at NGRI (Table 5), were comparable to the best in the world. Rare earth elements, Th and U were determined at ultra-trace concentration levels (between 0.01 and 1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in solid rock materials) even in ultramafic rocks using ICP-MS, after the samples were dissolved using a microwave digestion method²¹. Vijayalakshmi *et al.*²² carried out the precise estimation of common impurities in uranium by ICP-MS. Alonso *et al.*²³ modified a commercial ICP-MS instrument in order to work with radioactive materials in a glove box. They successfully analyzed a variety of nuclear radioactive materials which include fresh nuclear fuels, spent fuels and reprocessing solution for the precise elemental and isotopic analysis of lanthanides and actinides.

TIMS has been utilized for the determination of actinides such as U, Pu, Am and Cm for a long time. Although TIMS is one of the best techniques to perform isotope ratio measurements, it requires time-consuming sample preparations as well as long analysis time. Measurements of actinides by isotope dilution mass spectrometry (ID-MS) firstly require elemental separation between U, Pu, Am and Cm in order to eliminate isobaric interferences. Chartier *et al.*²⁴ described a method for the determination of Am and Cm in spent nuclear fuels by ID-ICP-MS and also ID-MS after separation by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). It has been concluded that although the accuracy of isotope ratio measurements by ICP-

MS is not as good as that obtained by TIMS, it is still adequate for isotope dilution analysis. Isotope dilution-ICP-MS is consequently an attractive alternative to techniques such as TIMS for the determination of Am and Cm in spent fuels due to its high throughput and shorter analysis time. Its use is still more interesting when precision requirements are less stringent as for waste management or environmental monitoring. These studies reveal that this technique is a suitable choice for the analysis of radioactive nuclear materials.

Table 4. Comparison of REE data ($\mu\text{g/g}$) obtained by INAA and ICP-MS for a couple of basaltic rocks from Globoke Lake, Siberian Platform, Russia

Element	GL-39		GL-41	
	INAA value ^a	ICP-MS value ^b	INAA value ^a	ICP-MS value ^b
La	25	23.86	28	25.66
Ce	48	50.79	51	52.69
Pr	ND	6.65	ND	6.40
Nd	26	28.21	28	28.25
Sm	5.8	5.84	6.0	6.27
Eu	2.0	1.90	2.0	1.73
Gd	ND	6.76	ND	6.24
Tb	0.9	0.87	1.0	0.98
Dy	ND	5.36	ND	5.00
Ho	ND	ND	ND	ND
Er	ND	2.38	ND	2.91
Tm	0.4	0.41	0.35	0.32
Yb	2.5	2.45	2.50	2.34
Lu	0.4	0.32	0.40	0.39

ND = not determined. ^aAt BARC, Mumbai. ^bAt NGRI using the method described in Ref. 16. Precision : ICP-MS <5% RSD for all REE; INAA <10% RSD for La, Ce, Nd, Sm, Yb, Lu, <15% RSD for Eu, Tb.

Table 5. REE, Th and U concentrations ($\mu\text{g/g}$) reported by NGRI in micro granite reference sample in (G-94) comparison with the assigned values and z-score values indicating the performance at NGRI in each case²⁰

Element	NGRI ICP-MS ^a	Assigned values ^b	z-score value	Performance of NGRI ^c
La	6.36	5.6	2.20	N
Ce	13.70	12.43	1.77	Y
Pr*	1.75	NA	NA	NA
Nd	8.87	7.32	3.57	N
Sm	2.27	2.13	0.91	Y
Eu	0.57	0.52	1.06	Y
Gd	3.12	2.78	1.80	Y
Tb	0.56	0.49	1.52	Y
Dy	3.46	3.40	0.25	Y
Ho	0.85	0.80	0.82	Y
Er	2.55	2.40	0.91	Y
Tm	0.38	0.37	0.27	Y
Yb	2.53	2.49	0.25	Y
Lu	0.42	0.39	0.69	Y
Th	2.20	1.68	4.18	N
U	0.45	0.40	1.51	Y

*For Pr, insufficient data were available or statistical assessment of the data was unfavourable (e.g. not normally distributed). ^cCategory no. 1 (pure geochemistry); Y = fell within acceptable range; N = fell outside acceptable range. z = score values better than ± 2 are considered satisfactory; NA = not available.

^aAverage of six values. ^bRef. 20.

The introduction of solutions into ICP is very convenient with relatively simple change over from one sample to another, and in many cases matrix matching of standards and samples is not required for obtaining reliable data. However, direct analysis of rock or mineral samples can provide additional information which is not available if a bulk solution analysis is carried out. This requirement has led to the development of a technique called laser ablation ICP-MS (LA-ICP-MS)²⁵. This technique was effectively used for the quantitative determination of major, minor and several trace elements including Th, U and REE in a variety of geological samples^{26,27}. Laser sample introduction method was also utilized for the analysis of liquid samples in conjunction with ICP-MS²⁸.

Development of sector field or high resolution-ICP-MS (HR-ICP-MS)

Commercially available ICP-MS instruments have been developed mainly around quadrupole mass filters, owing in part to the modest vacuum requirements, compact size and robustness. Due to limited mass resolution capability offered by quadrupole mass filters, ICP-MS technique suffers from several types of spectral interferences^{29,30}, which is the principal limitation of this technique for the analysis of complex materials like geological samples resulting in poor selectivity and sensitivity for a number of elements. Three types of undesirable ions form in the plasma which can coincide with mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of an isotope of interest causing false positive results. They are called spectral interferences caused by polyatomic ions originating from the combination of certain elements with plasma gas, atmospheric gases, water, reagents, and the sample, doubly-charged ions, and finally isobaric overlaps. The most effective solution to these problems is the use of double focusing mass analyzer consisting of an electrostatic analyzer in conjunction with magnetic sector analyzer instead of a quadrupole mass filter to obtain significant increase in mass resolution. This type of instrument is known as Sector Field or High Resolution-ICP-MS (HR-ICP-MS). These instruments offer a resolution of up to $M/\Delta M = 10000$ at 3% transmission which helps to overcome many spectral interferences observed in conventional ICP-MS^{31,32}.

Overview of HR-ICP-MS

A schematic diagram of a HR-ICP-MS (Thermo Elemental, UK) is shown in Fig. 1. This is a double-focusing system consisting of an ICP source, a sampling interface, an electrostatic analyzer (ESA), a magnetic sector analyzer (MSA) and a detector system. The sample solution is fed to the plasma through a nebulizer-spray-chamber system which is water-cooled to reduce solvent loading to the

Fig. 1. Schematic of a HR-ICP-MS (Thermo Elemental, UK).

plasma. The ICP source will ionize most elements including elements like hafnium that are difficult to be ionized with thermal sources⁵. Cooling of the nebulizer-spray-chamber system will minimize polyatomic ion formation (e.g. ArO^+ , MO^+ , etc.). Ions are extracted from the ion-sampling interface and injected into the field of electrostatic analyzer (ESA) which is an energy focusing device. The ESA in combination with MSA focuses ions with different energies on to the same point on the detector system. The spectrometer has the capability of adjustable resolution by changing the width of the source slit and the collector slit under computer control. This combination produces excellent flat-peak shapes at low resolution and in addition ensures good focusing across the entire mass range and full focal plane of multi-collector array. Maximum resolution is defined by the design of the mass spectrometer. A large mass dispersion enables greater resolving power with less signal reduction. Under resolving spectra will lead to an incomplete removal of interferences. Over resolving spectra will lead to an unnecessary loss of signal sensitivity. A 10000 RP is the industry standard high-resolution specification for inorganic mass spectrometers. However, an adjustable slit mechanism allows to obtain resolution settings well in excess of 10000 RP. This is required to resolve common interferences like ^{40}Ar on ^{80}Se and can be especially useful in the resolution of refractory metal oxides, for example, to eliminate the interferences of oxides of the light rare earth elements (LREEs) on heavy rare earth elements (HREEs). The analysis of ytterbium in a gadolinium matrix requires a resolving power of 13500 RP to resolve the interference of GdO on Yb (Fig. 2) for its accurate estimation. The detector system of single collector instrument consists of a dual detection system comprising of an on-axis Faraday collector and a fast switching off-axis pulse counting electron multiplier. This provides a working range of over nine orders of magnitude. The multiplier is automatically protected from signal overload during operation. This automatic ranging facility ensures that signals that are over-range on the multiplier are not lost but are immediately collected by the

Fig. 2. Separation of Yb peak from that of GdO at 135,000 RP.

Faraday collector. For isotope ratio measurement applications, multi-collector detection system is preferred because of the extremely precise and accurate isotope ratio data which can be obtained on a multi-collector detection system (typically < 0.002% RSD). This configuration incorporates a Faraday collector array. The off-axis Faraday collectors are independently adjustable with high-precision drives allowing quick and reproducible collector positions. The collectors can be positioned far apart enough for simultaneous detection of the isotopes of boron or close enough together for the collection of the isotopes of plutonium. The axial front Faraday is retractable, enabling pulse-counting detection on the electron multiplier. The multiplier can be operated independently or in conjunction with the off-axis front Faraday detectors of the multi-collector array.

The single collector HR-ICP-MS instruments will allow wide mass scans in a fast scanning mode, one single scan over the mass range 6–260 *m/z* takes about 300–500 ms. The capability to resolve multiple components within one mass unit permits more accurate measurements of ion abundance of specific elements, thus improving the detection limit for that element. The instrumental detection limits are improved by about three orders of magnitude when compared with conventional quadrupole-ICP-MS. For example, Table 6 presents the comparison of detection limits of rare earths, thorium, uranium and plutonium obtained by both these techniques. Currently HR-ICP-MS is undoubtedly the most sensitive instrumental analytical technique with detection limits for several metals in parts per quadrillion (ppq) range. It is expected that even lower detection limits will be obtained when a much longer integration time is adopted although such an approach will not be applicable for analysis on routine basis. More details are given by Bradshaw *et al.*³³ and Feldman *et al.*³⁴. This technology of combining an ICP source with a double-focussing magnetic sector analyzer in conjunction was independently reported first in 1989 by VG Elemental group³³ and JEOL group³⁵. However, a high resolution commercial instrument ‘Plasma Trace’ was the first to be introduced into the market in 1989 by VG Elemental, UK. Currently there are about six firms which are making HR-ICP-MS instruments and more than

300 HR-ICP-MS systems working in different laboratories around the world^{36,37}.

Table 6. Comparative detection limits obtained for rare earth elements and some actinides by conventional ICP-MS and HR-ICP-MS

Element/ Isotope	ICP-MS ng/ml (ppb) (1987 model) ^a	ICP-MS pg/ml (ppt) (1999 model) ^b	HR-ICP-MS fg/ml (ppq) (1994 model) ^c
¹³⁹ La	0.01	0.1	1.4
¹⁴⁰ Ce	0.02	0.4	2
¹⁴¹ Pr	0.01	0.1	1
¹⁴⁶ Nd	0.05	0.2	5.8
¹⁴⁷ Sm	0.07	0.02	5
¹⁵³ Eu	0.02	0.1	3
¹⁵⁷ Gd	0.04	0.15	5
¹⁵⁹ Tb	0.01	0.03	0.8
¹⁶³ Dy	0.02	0.1	2
¹⁶⁵ Ho	0.01	–	0.5
¹⁶⁶ Er	0.01	0.08	2
¹⁶⁹ Tm	0.01	0.1	0.8
¹⁷⁴ Yb	0.02	0.1	2
¹⁷⁵ Lu	0.01	0.1	0.9
²³² Th	0.01	0.2	1
²³⁸ U	0.01	0.1	0.7
²³⁹ Pu	–	–	5

^aRef. 17. ^bRef. 6. ^cRef. 44. NA = not available.

Analysis of REE, Th, Np, U and Pu by HR-ICP-MS

The extremely low detection limits (Table 6) at parts per quadrillion (ppq) levels have resulted from the extremely low background together with high analyte signal intensities and very high efficiency of the analyzer system. HR-ICP-MS with multiple collector has been extensively used recently for the measurement of isotopic compositions at high precision which is of great relevance to planetary, earth, ocean, and environmental sciences. Walder *et al.*³⁸ measured isotope ratios of Sr, Pb, Nd and Sm using ICP-MS with seven Faraday detectors. The relative standard deviation (RSD) of the ¹⁴³Nd/¹⁴⁴Nd ratio was found to be 0.0038% which was comparable to that obtainable by TIMS. Laser Ablation (LA) sample introduction was coupled with the HR-ICP-MS and evaluated for the precise and accurate determination of abundances of REE in zircon¹⁹.

ICP-MS analysis of lanthanides is known to be hampered by spectral and non-spectral interferences. Most of these spectral interferences can be resolved by using HR-ICP-MS (Fig. 2). Besides this, since the technique is extremely sensitive, samples having very low total dissolved solids (< 0.05%TDS) are currently being used for analysis in addition to the use of single and multiple internal standards, and matrix matching standard reference materials for calibration. These steps will reduce the non-spectral interferences or matrix effects to a large extent.

Since uranium and hydride form protonated uranium in the plasma, ²³⁸UH⁺ is a possible interference on ²³⁹Pu and

therefore it is important to control the protonated uranium formation in the plasma or use the high resolving power of HR-ICP-MS to resolve these two peaks. Sturpu *et al.*¹ used a mass resolution of 400 RP for the precise estimation of ²⁴⁰Pu / ²³⁹Pu isotope ratios and the total concentration of Pu in environmental samples by HR-ICP-MS. Hence, for the analysis of actinides resolution setting of 400 RP is sufficient as these elements have virtually no spectral interferences. Isotope-pairs with isobaric overlap require mass resolutions much higher than obtainable with even high resolution instruments (from $M/\Delta M = 75227$ for ¹⁴⁴Nd / ¹⁴⁴Sm to $M/\Delta M = 5854614$ for ¹⁶⁴Dy / ¹⁶⁴Er). Therefore, all isobaric overlaps cannot be resolved by HR-ICP-MS⁴⁰. The resolution settings required for various rare earth isotopes which are normally used for chemical analysis are given in Table 2. It can be observed that a resolution setting of about 13000 RP can resolve most of the spectral interferences encountered in the analysis of lanthanides.

A crucial point in the analysis of lanthanides and actinides is to find appropriate digestion method in order to avoid incomplete digestion. Especially, in the case of the determination of REE in silicate rocks, the sample preparation is not straight forward. Different dissolution methods involving open digestion, closed decomposition and fusion procedures are employed. Microwave induced decomposition procedures are found to be most effective for rapid dissolution of geological materials⁸.

Conclusion :

The above is an overview of some of the highlights of published work from different laboratories the world over including NGRI, accomplished so far in the analysis of REE, Th, U, Pu, Am and Cm in geological, nuclear and environmental materials using plasma source mass spectrometric techniques, namely, ICP-MS and HR-ICP-MS. Since its development in 1989, HR-ICP-MS has been applied virtually to all kinds of samples for characterization of elemental as well as isotopic compositions because of its ability to overcome most spectroscopic interferences, in particular when complex matrices, like geological, environmental, industrial and nuclear samples are analyzed. These modern instrumental analytical techniques have undoubtedly revolutionized the analysis of rare earth elements and some actinides in a variety of geological and environmental samples. Currently these two plasma source mass spectrometric techniques are playing a leading role in the analysis of not only lanthanides and actinides but also several other elements across the periodic table in a wide variety of matrices with several advantages over INAA, ICP-AES and TIMS techniques. With the widespread popularity currently that the HR-ICP-MS is enjoying there is a possibility that

this technique, particularly the multi-collector systems will replace TIMS in high precision research areas, such as planetary, earth, ocean and nuclear sciences. Coupling of laser ablation sample introduction accessory to both ICP-MS and HR-ICP-MS may find wider application in earth and nuclear sciences. HPLC coupled to these plasma mass spectrometric techniques will further enhance their importance, particularly in nuclear and environmental research.

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